

Fabrication and Characterization of AZ91/CNT Magnesium Matrix Composite processed by squeeze infiltration

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SUMMARY

CNT reinforced AZ91 metal matrix composites were fabricated by the squeeze infiltrated method. The squeeze infiltration technique was a proper method to fabricate magnesium matrix composites reducing casting defects such as pores and matrix/reinforcement interface separation etc. Improved tensile and creep properties were obtained by reinforcing CNT to magnesium alloys

Keywords: Carbon nano tube, Magnesium, Metal matrix composite, Fabrication

Introduction

Properties of magnesium alloys have been improved by impurity reduction, surface treatment and alloy design, thus the usage for the magnesium alloys has been extended recently. However there still remain barriers for the application of magnesium alloys as engineering materials. Especially the properties at elevated temperature are known to be degraded significantly. Carbon nano tubes(CNTs) are one of the most exciting new materials to have been discovered in past years.[1] Their remarkable properties have attracted intense interest from the scientific community, as well as from the industry. They are the stiffest and strongest fibers known, with Young's modulus as high as 1TPa and tensile strength of up to 63GPa. High stiffness, elastic modulus and low density make CNTs good candidate for use as reinforcement in composites materials, especially metal matrix composite.[2,3] There are two major parameters for fabrication of CNTs/magnesium matrix composite. First, the uniform dispersion of CNTs in magnesium matrix is a very important factor. CNTs are tangled with each other by Van der Waals force, so the process for CNT dispersion must be applied to fabricate sound composites. Also, the preform and the composite should be produced properly to optimize the effect of CNT as reinforcement. In the present work, CNT/magnesium matrix composites were investigated to improve mechanical properties of the magnesium alloys.

Experimental procedure

CNTs/magnesium matrix composite was fabricated by the squeeze infiltration method. The matrix alloy is AZ91 (Mg-9mass%Al-0.7%Zn) magnesium alloy and the reinforcement is multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) with a diameter of 5~20nm

and a length of ~10 μ m. To prepare preform, silica colloidal inorganic binder, starch organic binder and polyacrylamide were dispersed in dilute water and a vacuum suction method was used to reduce closed microporosity. The packing rate of the reinforcement in preform was about 15% and it was roughly controlled by the vacuum suction pressure. The preform was placed in the electrical furnace heated at 450°C and kept for 4hr to eliminate the retained humidity and the organic binder. Prior to squeeze infiltration, the mold and preform were preheated at 450°C. The molten alloy was superheated up to 940°C, and poured into the preform. The pressure being applied by the punch on the molten metal was 70MPa. Microstructure characteristics were performed using transmission electron microscope (TEM). General metallographic procedure was followed with the etchant of 2% oxalic acid and 98% ethanol mixture. Micro-Vickers hardness and tensile tests were carried out to investigate the mechanical properties of the unreinforced alloy and the composites. Initial engineering strain rate was of 2.0×10^{-4} /min for tensile tests at room temperature and elevated temperature (150°C). Creep test were also carried out at stress level of 100MPa at a temperature of 150°C.

Results and discussion

Microstructural

Fig. 1 shows SEM and TEM images of MWCNT microstructure. The micrographs reveal reasonably uniform distribution with random orientation of the CNTs (Fig. 1a). Bright field TEM images of the composite shown in Fig. 1(b) reveal that carbon nanotubes are pinned at the sub grain boundaries of the magnesium matrix. It is also observed that there are no free dislocations in the sub grain, probably due to the dislocation being captured by low angle tilt or twist boundaries at the sub grain as these experience reduced energy.

Fig. 1 Microstructure of MWCNT (as fabricated)

References

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